

Influence of process parameters on properties of chromium oxide deposited by reactive HiPIMS

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Abstract. Chromium oxide coatings appear to be a potentially attractive material since its good tribological properties at high temperature. Coatings were prepared by reactive high power impulse magnetron sputtering (HiPIMS). Coating depositions were carried out on cold work and hot work tool steel samples. To achieve ion bombardment of the growing coating, bias on the substrate or positive kick on the sputtering target were applied. The impact of these methods on the structure and properties of the coating was then investigated.

The surface and cross-section of coatings were examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The structure of the coatings was studied using X-ray diffraction (XRD). The influence of the coating process on surface roughness and the presence of coating defects was further studied using phase shifting interferometry and optical light microscopy. Tribological tests were performed using the pin-on-disc method at room temperature and high temperature using Al₂O₃ counterbodies. During tests at high temperatures, the coatings exhibited low wear and stable friction, predisposing them to use in applications at elevated temperatures.

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1. Introduction:

In many applications, such as aviation or energy, friction occurs at very high temperatures. The presence of high temperatures when the materials are in contact prevents the use of conventional lubricants to reduce friction. The mechanical properties of the materials also degrade at high temperatures and oxidation occurs more rapidly. These factors can lead to an increase of wear

and friction. One possible way to improve tribological properties at high temperatures is to use tribological coatings on the surface of contact materials.

A widely studied group of high-temperature tribological coatings is based on the application of solid lubricants, which either form the coatings themselves or are formed on their surfaces at high temperatures [1,2]. Commonly studied solid lubricants are soft metals, transition metal dichalcogenide and for the highest temperatures also binary and ternary oxides. The challenge faced by solid lubricants is the fact that most of them work only in a limited range of temperatures. To cover the whole range of applicable temperatures, coatings that use the synergetic effect of multiple different solid lubricants need to be designed.

Chromium oxide Cr_2O_3 coatings appears to be a potentially attractive material, since their good tribological properties were recorded in the temperature range up to 1000 °C [3–5]. The coatings in these articles were deposited on Inconel 718 alloy using the cathodic arc evaporation method. To improve the properties of the coatings, annealing (controlled oxidation) was further carried out at temperatures of 960 to 1000 °C for 2 hours. After annealing, the hardness of the coatings decreased and their tribological properties improved significantly. The friction coefficient ranged between 0.2 and 0.3 across the entire range of temperatures tested from 25 to 1000 °C. These properties were also found when the coating was reused.

High power impulse magnetron sputtering represents a modern approach to achieve significantly higher ionisation of sputtered material in comparison to DC magnetron sputtering. The higher ionisation and high-ion bombardment associated with it led to significant improvements in the coated layer, as well as significant changes in the reactive magnetron sputtering process [6].

In the presented study, chromium oxide films were prepared by reactive HiPIMS. To utilize high ionisation, both substrate bias and positive kick were used for deposition control. The influence of process parameters on the tribological properties of the coating was further tested.

2. Materials and methods

Chromium oxides were prepared by magnetron sputtering in HiPIMS mode. The 50 mm 99.95 % chromium target supplied by the Kurt.J.Lesker company was used as the source of chromium. 20 mm discs of 1.2379 tool steel and 25 mm discs of 1.2344 hot working tool steel were used as substrates for the tested samples. The surfaces of the substrates were ground with SiC sandpaper and polished with 1 μm diamond paste applied on a hard cloth prior to deposition. Furthermore, the silicon wafer with a diameter of 76 mm and a thickness of 0.5 mm was also coated for purposes of analysis by scanning electron microscopy.

2.1 HiPIMS process

Coating depositions were performed on a laboratory HVM Plasma Flexilab 3 sputtering system equipped with three magnetron cathodes. The vacuum chamber was evacuated to a pressure of 4×10^{-3} Pa prior to the start of the deposition. Argon (99.999 at%) was used as a working gas with a flow of 20 sccm resulting in a working pressure of ~ 0.9 Pa. The substrates were placed on a rotation table and heated to a temperature of 400 °C for the duration of deposition. The average power of 150 W was applied during deposition on one cathode with Cr target (99.95 at%). The HiPIMS pulse width was 40 μs , the applied voltage was 600 V and the maximum current was roughly 17 A (~ 0.8 A/cm²). The flow of oxygen (99.999 at%) was 0.7 sccm and the deposition lasted 2 h. Two sets of samples were prepared for the purposes of this study. During the first deposition (referred to as BIAS), a bias of 200 V was used during the preparation of chromium

oxide. In the second deposition (referred to as KICK) no bias was used but a kick with a width of 60 μs and voltage of 150 V was used. The deposition parameters are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Parameters HiPIMS process.

Parameter	Value
Ar flow rate	20 sccm
O ₂ flow rate	0,7 sccm
Pulse voltage	600 V
Peak Current	17 A
Average power	150 W
Pulse width	40 μs
Duty cycle	~1,3 %

2.2. Coating Characterisation and Testing

The thickness of the coating was measured using the calotest method on the CSM calotest tester with the use of a 30mm ball and 1 μm diamond suspension as an abrasive.

The Rockwell indentation test (Mercedes test) for the evaluation of adhesion of coatings was performed using the Struers Duramin 40AC3 hardness test.

The surface morphology was evaluated before and after deposition to determine the influence of deposition control techniques on the roughness of the surface using a Sensofar five-axis optical profilometer. Phase shift interferometry (PSI) was used as an acquisition technique with 50x magnification. The root mean square roughness Sq was chosen as the main parameter compared.

Tribological tests were conducted using the pin-on-disc THT CSM Instruments tribometer. The tests were carried out with an Al₂O₃ counter body, a 6 mm diameter ball, at room temperature, and a high temperature of 600 ° C. The 5000 laps were used for these tests. The applied load was 2 N-for the 5000 laps tests. The Coefficient of friction (COF) was calculated by tribometer software from applied load and measured friction force. The wear of the counter body surface was analysed using an Olympus DSX1000 digital microscope after the test. For all combinations tested, a specific wear rate was calculated from the equation:

$$k = \frac{V}{F \cdot s}$$

where k is the specific wear rate [mm^3/Nm], V is the wear volume [mm^3], F is the normal load [N] and s is the sliding distance [m]. The wear volume was obtained by multiplying the area of the wear track cross section, measured with a Sensofar S Neox five-axes optical profilometer, by the circumference of the wear track.

Observations of the coatings cross sections were carried out by JEOL JSM-7600F scanning electron microscopy using a 15 KV acceleration voltage. Cross sections were obtained by fracture of the coated Si wafer.

XRD patterns were measured using the Rigaku Ultima IV X-ray diffractometer (Rigaku, Japan, CuK α radiation, NiK β filter, scintillation detector, Bragg-Brentano arrangement) in ambient atmosphere under constant conditions (40 kV, 40 mA, scanning range 15-80° 2 θ , scanning speed 3.2°/min).

3. Results and Discussion

The measured coating thickness was 1.95 μm for KICK and 2.3 μm for BIAS. These thicknesses correspond to the deposition rate of 0.975 $\mu\text{m}/\text{h}$ for the former and 1.15 $\mu\text{m}/\text{h}$ for the latter. This is a relatively high deposition rate for reactive sputtering and is comparable with the deposition rate of pure chromium in HiPIMS mode with similar applied power on the same coating aperture. The results of the Rockwell indentation test are presented in Figure 1. An acceptable adhesion HF2 was observed for the KICK coating and HF3 for the BIAS coating. The adhesion of the coating can be considered adequate and is comparable with that of a range of hard coatings prepared by magnetron sputtering.

Figure 1. Rockwell indentation test: a) KICK coating (HF 2) and b) BIAS coating (HF 3).

The results of the measurements of Sq measurements (root mean square height) for both coated material before and after coating are listed in Table 2. In the case of tool steel 1.2379, the surface roughness is improved by coating process due to smoothing of exposed chromium carbides in the steel. These carbides are not present in steel 1.2344, resulting in a lower roughness in the uncoated state and a small increase in roughness after coating. In both cases the BIAS coating obtained slightly lower roughness.

Table 2. Root mean square roughness Sq of measured samples

Sample	Uncoated	coated
1.2379 BIAS	9.5±0.7 nm	4.2±0.6 nm
1.2379 KICK	10.4±2.6 nm	5.3±0.5 nm
1.2344 BIAS	5.2±0.6 nm	5.05±0.3 nm
1.2344 KICK	3.4±0.25 nm	5.3±0.5 nm

Tribological testing at room temperature showed significant differences between BIAS and KICK coatings. The BIAS coating did not survive the test. The coating immediately collapsed, resulting in an increased coefficient of friction and wear. The tests were stopped after coating breakdown, as subsequent contact occurred between ball and substrate. The substrate material used did not affect the tribological test in this case. However, the KICK coating performed adequately during the test room temperature tests. It stabilises at the friction coefficient approximately 0.4.

Figure 2. Course of a) the friction coefficient and b) specific wear rate of coatings tested at room temperature

The specific wear rate of KICK coatings at room temperature is very low. Although the coating surface was relatively well polished prior to testing, the wear track was barely observable. It results in a significant statistical error on the measured values visible in Figure 2b.

At 600 °C, both coatings performed similarly, representing a significant improvement of the tribological properties of the BIAS coating. The COF was slightly lower than at room temperature and stabilized around 0.3. The specific wear rate of both coatings at 600 °C (Figure 3b) is also comparable. Significant standard deviations are present due to inconsistent wear, which is sometimes accompanied by the growth of the material on the wear track. Overall coatings exhibited excellent wear resistance at high temperatures. BIAS coatings at higher temperatures further oxidize.

Figure 3. a) Course of the friction coefficient and b) specific wear rate of coatings tested at 600 °C

The cross section of the coating is presented in Figure 4. As is visible, there are significant differences between two deposition processes. In case of KICK coating, the columnar structure is well observable. The BIAS coating appears to be somewhat denser. Based on these observations, it can be thought that the bias used leads to higher kinetic energy of implanted ions. Higher ion flux during this deposition could also explain lower surface roughness achieved on BIAS coatings [7]. The potential reduction in arcing on the sputtering target during the KICK process didn't have a significant effect on surface roughness or coating structure [8].

XRD observations reveal that the BIAS coating is primarily comprised of phase Cr_3O , while the KICK coating is comprised of Cr_3O , Cr_2O_3 , and CrO_2 . These differences could explain the tribological behavior since at high temperatures Cr_3O reacts with oxygen and forms Cr_2O_3 which leads to an improvement of the tribological properties compared to room temperature.

Figure 4. SEM image of cross section of a) KICK coating and b) BIAS coating on Si substrate

4. Conclusion

The presented study examined the influence of process control parameters on the properties of chromium oxide coatings. Results can be summarised as follows:

- Coating prepared with bias doesn't perform at room temperature, however at high temperatures it achieves low specific wear rate and low coefficient of friction.
- Utilising kick leads to extremely low wear rate at room temperature accompanied by low and stable friction. At high temperatures performance is comparable with bias coating.
- Based on observation of the coating structure, it can be expected that the presence of Cr₂O₃ and CrO₂ positively affects the tribological properties.
- These oxides were present only after the application of a positive kick during the deposition.

Chromium oxide coatings prepared by HiPIMS proven their potential as high temperatures tribological coatings. Further research is needed to examine the causes of differences in the performance of the deposited coating, as well as to further optimize the coating process.

Data Availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in repository ZENODO at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16363466>.

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